

French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety

Investigate, evaluate, protect

**1st International Workshop
on Horizon scanning for Plant health**

**9&10 April 2024
Maisons-Alfort, France**

A "One Health" Agency

- Created in 2010
- 1400 employees
- Annual budget of 160 million €

Scientific expert appraisals at ANSES

Multidisciplinary

All the necessary scientific skills are brought together

Collective

All the experts' different points of view are expressed in order to form a conclusion

Adversarial

The various evidence is debated in light of the scientific knowledge and related uncertainties

800 experts from outside the Agency (toxicology, epidemiology, medicine, occupational health, biostatistics, physical chemistry, human and social sciences, etc.)

Selected by **public calls for applications**

Subject to **public declarations of interests**

Compliance with the **charter for health-related expert appraisal** and the **NF X 50-110 standard**

Implementation of the ethical framework throughout the expert appraisals

Producing scientific knowledge

The ANSES laboratories: **watchdogs and reference bodies** in France and beyond

Three fields of research:

- Plant health
- Animal health and welfare
- Food safety, including drinking water

Laboratories recognised for their **scientific excellence**, with **reference mandates** for numerous pathogens and chemical contaminants in animal health, plant health and food safety.

>100 national, European or international reference mandates

9 laboratories on 16 sites 700 employees

Examining marketing authorisation applications

- Veterinary medicinal products
- Plant protection products
- Biocidal products
- Fertilisers and growing media

Before any product can be placed on the market, ANSES **assesses its effectiveness and risks** for human and animal health, and the environment. It is also responsible for **examining marketing authorisation applications**.

At European level, ANSES is fully engaged and contributes to the development of new assessment methods for regulated products.

A specific organisation based on:

- Two different departments within the Agency.
- ANSES's **expert groups** for the assessment.
- The French Agency for **Veterinary Medicinal Products** (part of ANSES) for veterinary medicinal products.

How ANSES works

anses

The Anses plant health missions

CONNAÎTRE, ÉVALUER, PROTÉGER

Investigate, evaluate, protect

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The challenges of plant health

A global context overall more and more challenging:

- Increase in global plants & plants products' trade: frequency, quantities/volumes & diversity
- Impact of climate change
- New and emerging cultural practices and technical itineraries
- Growing concern about health & environment issues linked to plant production products (PPP)

New and emerging issues on:

- All types of pests/pathogens: viroïds, viruses, bacteria, fungi & oomycetes, nematodes, insects & mites, invasives plants
- Conventional PPP & bio-inspired ones
- Crops, forests, wild & urban plants
- European & overseas France

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Plant health at Anses

A global approach at the Agency's level:

- Pests-pathogens / plants & environment interactions
- Laboratories & other Anses' directions:
 - Research & reference
 - Support to surveillance
 - Risk assessment
 - PPP evaluation & authorization
- Sanitary, economic & social contexts

ANSES Organisation Chart – April 17th 2023

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Divisions involved (others than Research & Reference)

- Risk Assessment Direction (Science for expertise Division):
 - > Expert panel **'Biological Risks for Plant Health'**
 - (+ Scientific and technical support from PLH laboratory)
 - 'Plant protection products-vigilance'** unit (UPO)
- Regulated Products Assessment Direction (Regulated Products Division):
 - Hazards & risks towards humans, animals or the environment evaluation** (EU & Fr regulations)
 - Agronomical interest/value of PPP, fertilisers & non-indigenous macroorganisms**
 - > Expert panel **'Plant Protection Substances & Products, Bio-inspired control'**
- Marketing Authorization Direction (Regulated Products Division) :
 - Marketing authorization management
 - Authorization for **experimentation/testing** of PPP & fertilisers & their adjuvants

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Specific missions – Reference Mandates

3 missions specifically performed by PLH lab:

- 2 in Angers : GMO detection (BVO) & Risk assessment (ERB)
- 1 in Clermont-Ferrand : post-entry quarantine ('quarantaine')

All units : NRL

3 units : EURL

- Entomology & Botany (Montpellier) : 'insects & mites'
- with AGES (Austria)
- Nematology (Rennes) : 'plant parasitic nematodes' with ILVO (Belgium)
- Mycology (Nancy) : 'fungi & oomycetes'

Geographic and thematic organization: specific missions, EURL & research partnerships

Research partnerships

3 partnerships:

Nematology unit:

- NemAlliance scientific partnership (UMR IGEPP, INRAE-Institut Agro-Université de Rennes)

Mycology unit

- USC INRAE (Dpt ECODIV) & LabEx ARBRE

RAPT unit

- DIAGEPITROP research partnership (UMR PVBMT Cirad-La Réunion university)

Geographic and thematic organization: specific missions, EURL & research partnerships

RÉPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE
Liberté
Égalité
Fraternité

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The pluridisciplinary Lyon Laboratory

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USC INRAE 1438 CASPER : Characterization & monitoring of resistances to PPP

EAS : Epidemiology & support to surveillance

The Lyon Laboratory :

- participates to **coordination/steering** of the **French national epidemiological surveillance for plant health**
- provides a **transversal support in épidemiology and surveillance** for all Anses labs and directions

- participates to the **surveillance to PPP**
- contributes to the **surveillance & controls campains** on resistance to PP
- investigates the corresponding mechanisms (at both phenotypique & genotypique levels) & develops corresponding **detection methods**

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RÉPUBLIQUE FRANÇAISE
Liberté
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Fraternité

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Thank you for your attention

www.anses.fr

Science driving a safer, healthier world for all

Horizon scanning for biosecurity: a false dawn?

Professor Philip Hulme

C **BRAS**

Centre for One-Biosecurity Research Analysis and Synthesis
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Lincoln University
Lincoln 7647, New Zealand
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Conceptual basis for invasive species risk assessment

Risk assessment is a scientifically based process to identify hazards, characterize their adverse impacts, evaluate the level of exposure of a target to those hazards and estimate the risk

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Limits of biosecurity knowledge

Likelihood of species invasion	Much data/ knowledge	<p style="text-align: center;">Ambiguity</p> <p>e.g. Contending experts/fields Incommensurable priorities</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Risk</p> <p>e.g. Familiar systems Known invasive species</p>	
	Little data/ knowledge	<p style="text-align: center;">Ignorance</p> <p>e.g. Unanticipated effects Evolution in organism</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Complexity</p> <p>e.g. Complex non-linear systems Human element in causal models</p>	
		Little data/ knowledge		Much data/ knowledge
		Consequences of species invasion		

Chapter 23

BIOSECURITY: THE CHANGING FACE OF INVASION BIOLOGY

Philip E. Hulme
The Bio-Protection Research Centre, Lincoln University PO Box 84, Christchurch, New Zealand

Fifty Years of Invasion Ecology: The Legacy of Charles Elton, 1st edition, Edited by David M. Richardson
© 2013 by Blackwell Publishing Ltd

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Tools to address limits of biosecurity knowledge

Likelihood of species invasion	Much data/ knowledge	<p style="text-align: center;">Ambiguity</p> <p>e.g. Contending experts/fields Incommensurable priorities</p> <p style="color: red; text-align: center;">Qualitative approaches e.g. Deliberation 7 Questions interviews</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Risk</p> <p>e.g. Familiar systems Known invasive species</p> <p style="color: red; text-align: center;">Quantitative approaches e.g. Trend analysis Environmental scanning</p>	
	Little data/ knowledge	<p style="text-align: center;">Ignorance</p> <p>e.g. Unanticipated effects Evolution in organism</p> <p style="color: red; text-align: center;">Foresight approaches e.g. Horizon scanning Delphi technique</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Complexity</p> <p>e.g. Complex non-linear systems Human element in causal models</p> <p style="color: red; text-align: center;">Semi-quantitative approaches e.g. Axes of uncertainty Driver mapping</p>	
		Little data/ knowledge		Much data/ knowledge
		Consequences of species invasion		

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Horizon scanning one of several future thinking tools

What is horizon scanning?

The systematic examination of potential threats, opportunities and likely future developments to identify early weak signals that may evolve into emerging issues but are not yet present in current-day research or media.

Relies on intuition and insight – which can feel counterintuitive to those who are more practiced in evidence based strategic thinking.

Horizon scanning is the foundation of a strategic foresight process and is often found at the beginning of the forward-looking activity.

Plenty of guidance on horizon scanning

What aspects should horizon scanning encompass?

Systematic review of horizon scanning in invasions

Undertook systematic search for articles in Web of Knowledge (all databases) published between 1980-2024 that were found with the following topic search term

("horizon scan*") and ("invasive species" or "non-native species" or biosecurity or "biological invasions" or "alien species" or "non-indigenous species" or "exotic species")

Found **91 articles**

Rejected articles where:

- Horizon scans were used and identified invasive species as a future problem
- General reviews regarding biosecurity and invasions that mentioned horizon scans
- Species listing for an area to support future horizon scans
- Description of tools that could be used for horizon scanning

Retained **53 articles**

What aspects have horizon scanning encompassed

What aspects have horizon scanning encompassed

What approaches have these studies used

Driver mapping: used to identify the political, economic, societal, technological, legislative and environmental **drivers** shaping the future policy environment and distinguish between certain and uncertain outcomes resulting from the action of drivers

Environmental scans: used to identify the identity, pathways and potential impacts of alien species currently outside of a region but with the potential to establish in the near future that are often ranked in a prioritisation exercise to classify their **state** as biosecurity threats.

Horizon scans: used to capture emerging issues using an interdisciplinary team to gather ideas about trends and events shaping the future, score the ideas against pre-specified criteria and rescore following a Delphic process to highlight potential trade-offs in policy **responses**.

Roadmapping: used to create a set of common questions or issues relevant to biological invasions in order to set out and prioritise the steps required to achieve the vision and to describe what the future will be like if they are delivered

Drivers: Development of multi-driver invasion maps

a DRIVERS

b RATING DRIVERS

c RATING PAIRS OF DRIVERS

Sustainability Science (2021) 16:1617–1639
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11222-021-10063-6>

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Alternative futures for global biological invasions

Nuria Roura Pascual¹, Brian Leung^{1,4}, Wolfgang Rabitsch^{1,4}, Lucas Rutting^{1,5}, Joost Verweert^{1,6}, Sven Bacher⁷, Stefan Dullinger⁸, Karl Heinz Erb⁹, Jonathan M. Jeschke^{10,11}, Stelios Katsanevakis¹², Ingeborg Kühn^{13,14}, Bernd Lorenz¹⁵, Andrew M. Liebhold^{16,17}, Michael Odenwetter¹⁸, Anibal Pauchard^{19,20}, Garry D. Peterson²¹, Helen E. Roy²², Hanno Seebens²³, Marten Winter²⁴, Mark A. Burgelman²⁵, Florin Găvruta^{26,27}, Philipp E. Hulme²⁸, Roshan P. Kuttel²⁹, Guillaume Lacroix^{30,31}, Malinda A. McGeoch³², Gregory M. Ruiz³³, Riccardo Scaleri³⁴, Michael R. Spurgeon³⁵, Britny von Holle³⁶, Franz Essi^{37,38}

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Abstract
 Scenario analysis has emerged as a key tool to analyze complex and uncertain future socio-ecological developments. However, currently existing global scenarios (assessments of how the world may develop) have neglected biological invasions, a major threat to biodiversity and the economy. Here, we use a novel participatory process to develop a diverse set of global biological invasions scenarios spanning a wide range of plausible global futures through to 2050. We adapted the widely used “two axes” scenario analysis approach to develop four families of four scenarios each, resulting in 16 scenarios that were later clustered into four contrasting sets of futures. Our analysis highlights that socioeconomic developments and technological innovations have the potential to shape biological invasions, in addition to well-known drivers, such as climate and human land use change and global trade. Our scenarios partially align with the shared socioeconomic pathways created by the climate change research community. Several factors that drive differences in biological invasions were underrepresented in the shared socioeconomic pathways, in particular, the implementation of biosecurity policies. We argue that including factors related to public, environmental awareness and technological and trade developments in global scenarios and models is essential to adequately consider biological invasions in global environmental assessment and thereby obtain a more integrative picture of future socio-ecological developments.

Keywords Alien species · Biodiversity models · Environmental scenarios · Future narratives · Global environmental change · Impact · Management

Introduction
 Biological invasions are recognized as a major driver of biodiversity loss (Pascual et al. 2020). Invasive alien species (IAS) can threaten native biota and alter ecosystem functioning, disrupt the delivery of ecosystem services and cause extensive social and economic impacts (Dudgeon et al. 2006; Simberloff et al. 2013). The number of alien species continues to increase globally with no sign of saturation despite efforts to halt invasions (Shefferson et al. 2017). Advances have been made in understanding the direct drivers of biological invasions, such as ecological determinants (Simberloff et al. 2013) and anthropogenic factors, including climate change (Hulme 2017), global trade (Riley et al. 2015) and human disturbance (Spear et al. 2013). However, it is still unclear how these direct drivers are shaped by social developments and how indirect social drivers may determine the future influence of biological invasions (e.g. Lortie and Allen 2013). A better understanding of how social change may determine biological changes is a prerequisite to understand and effectively manage biological invasions in the Anthropocene (Hulst et al. 2020).
 Scenario analysis provides a systematic method to assess how complex interactions among many drivers of change

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 Extended data material available on the last page of this article.

State: Environmental scanning of future species risk

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 DOI: 10.1007/s11246-018-1427-7

PRIMARY RESEARCH ARTICLE WILEY *Global Change Biology*

Developing a list of invasive alien species likely to threaten biodiversity and ecosystems in the European Union

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³⁹INRAE, France, France
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But are such lists useful and have impact?

CRIMINAL PLANTS IN THE UK

IT IS CONSIDERED AN OFFENCE TO LET THIS PLANTS GROW IN YOUR GARDEN

 BROAD-LEAVED DOCK highly invasive and hosts many unwanted garden pests		
 RHODODENDRON PONTICUM invasive species that grows high and wide, outcompeting native plants		
 NEW ZEALAND PIGMYWEED forms dense mats that kills any native species in its path		

Response: Horizon scanning of emerging research

iScience **CellPress**
OPEN ACCESS

Review
Emerging advances in biosecurity to underpin human, animal, plant, and ecosystem health

Philip E. Hulme,^{1,2,3} Jacqueline R. Boggs,⁴ Rachelle N. Berry,⁵ Jonathan P. Bray,⁶ Naomi Cogger,⁷ Margaret K. Dharami,⁸ Susanna C. Fivay Smith,⁹ Nigel P. French,¹⁰ Andrea Grant,¹¹ Chad L. Hewitt,¹² Eliane E. Jones,¹³ Phil J. Lester,¹⁴ and Peter J. Leach¹⁵*

SUMMARY
One Biosecurity is an interdisciplinary approach to policy and research that builds on the interconnections between human, animal, plant, and ecosystem health to effectively prevent and mitigate the impacts of invasive alien species. To support this approach requires that key cross-sectoral research innovations be identified and prioritized. Following an interdisciplinary horizon scan for emerging research that underpins One Biosecurity, four major breakthrough advances were identified: implementation of new surveillance technologies; adopting state-of-the-art sensors connected to the Internet of Things; deployable, handheld molecular and genomic testing tools; the incorporation of wellbeing and diverse human values into biosecurity decision-making; and sophisticated socio-environmental models and data capture. The relevance and applicability of these innovations to address threats from pathogens, pests, and weeds in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems emphasize the opportunity to build critical mass around interdisciplinary teams at a global scale that can rapidly advance science solutions targeting biosecurity threats.

INTRODUCTION
Invasive alien pathogens, pests, and weeds pose a significant challenge to the environment worldwide and mismanagement results in huge global economic costs.^{1–3} Biosecurity covers all activities aimed at managing the introduction of alien species to a particular region and mitigating their impacts should they become established. It includes the implementation of international sanitary and phytosanitary standards, border inspection, pest border surveillance, incursion response and long-term management of invasive alien pathogens, pests, and weeds.⁴ There is the potential for the economic, ecological, and effective management of risks posed by introduced pests and diseases to the economy, environment and human health to be fundamentally enhanced by interdisciplinary activity that underpins human, animal, plant, and ecosystem health (see Fig. 1 for definition).

Nevertheless, despite fundamental similarities in the invasion process of pathogens, pests, and weeds, in comparison to other threat agents, animal, or plant health, government policies and regulations, research, and industry generally take a siloed approach to biosecurity defined by sectoral and taxonomic divisions. Although there have been calls to foster stronger human values integration within a One Health umbrella,^{5–7} there is increasing recognition that One Health remains largely focused on human health, and animal and human health, respectively, to ensure, while plant and ecosystem health considerations remain poorly integrated in terrestrial systems and are virtually absent in aquatic systems.^{8–10} Similarly, the integration of social aspects of biosecurity and disease management appear to be routinely ignored in the literature of One Health.¹¹ The many drivers of biological invasions that affect human, animal, plant, and ecosystem health are societal issues such as rapid globalization, human population growth, urbanization, land-use and tourism, international trade, or civil conflict and the relative contributions of these socio-economic drivers remain poorly quantified (Fig. 1).¹²

In response, the concept of One Biosecurity has been developed to foster an interdisciplinary approach to biosecurity policy and research, building on interconnection between human, animal, plant, and ecosystem health to prevent and mitigate the impacts of invasive alien species.¹³ The development of

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Integrating science across sectors and interventions

	Offshore risk 			
molecular and genomic tools 	Phylogenetics identify source regions for pathogens	eNA sampling of ballast water for invasive species	Testing waterways for alien pathogens and pests	DNA analysis identifies emergence pesticide resistance
human values and wellbeing 	Establishing trusted relationships with exporters	Building tourist biosecurity compliance	Engagement of citizen scientists for early detection	Incorporating values and wellbeing in pest control planning
sophisticated modelling 	Network models of shipping traffic to profile risk	Agent-based models of tourists moving through country	Spatiotemporal models of landscape scale pest spread	Proof-of-absence models following eradication
surveillance technologies 	RFID tracking of shipping containers and contents	eNose to detect pest odours in shipping containers	IoT tracking of national-scale livestock movements	Realtime AI photo identification of pests in traps

Response: Horizon scanning of emerging challenges

Importance of interdisciplinarity in horizon scanning

But interdisciplinary not always a priority

Freshwater invasion biologists Marine invasion biologists Plant invasion biologists

Vertebrate invasion biologists Insect invasion biologists

Conservation biologist

Vertebrate invasion biologists

Response: Roadmap for top issues in invasions

Management of Biological Invasions (2014) Volume 4, Issue 3, 1-20
 doi:10.1007/s10841-014-9811-0
 © 2014 by Springer Science+Business Media Dordrecht

Tackling Invasive Alien Species in Europe: the Top 20 Issues

Joe M. Callaway^{1*}, Jan-Robert Blom², Tony H. Blackburn³, Peter Borer⁴, Philip Borer⁵, Keith Cherrett⁶, James T. A. Cook⁷, John Early⁸, Leonard Edmunds⁹, Cathal O'Donoghue¹⁰, Jackson Hoggan¹¹, Percy Hoggan¹², Chris Hoggan¹³, Stephen Hoggan¹⁴, Philip H. Hoggan¹⁵, Stephen Hoggan¹⁶, Hugh J. Macdonald¹⁷, Paul McInerney¹⁸, Michael Millard¹⁹, Paul L. Moran²⁰, David Murray²¹, Jonathan Newman²², Brian O'Connell²³, Maria O'Farrell²⁴, Colleen O'Flynn²⁵, Roger O'Keefe²⁶, Tom R. Squires²⁷, Anthony Richardson²⁸, Helen Roy²⁹, Richard Shaw³⁰, John L. C. H. van Valkenburg³¹, Ulad Weyfer³², Frances Williams³³ and Frances E. Lucy³⁴

Abstract
 Invasive alien species (IAS) are considered to be one of the major threats to native biodiversity, with the World Conservation Union (IUCN) listing them among the 'top 100 threats to biodiversity'. It is estimated that 17% of the 12,000 alien species in Europe will increase in the coming years. In order to assess the current picture regarding IAS in Europe and to determine the areas that need to be most urgently addressed regarding these dangerous species, the international Partnership for Invasive Species (PPIS) conference was convened in Ireland in April 2013. Delegates from throughout Europe and around the world were invited to discuss the conference. These completed scientific, applied research, policy makers, practitioners and representatives of diverse groups. In addition, the conference also provided an opportunity for the results of the expert dialogue to be widely shared by identifying the Top 20 IAS issues in Europe. This session also drew attention to individual actions and how best to deal with the most serious threats. The Top 20 issues were considered separately in a total of 200 presentations and should also be used to support policy makers in key European Union legislation.

Key words: IAS legislation, awareness, early warning, economic analysis, better science, knowledge exchange, rapid response, risk assessment, monitoring.

Summary

- Futures Thinking is a core component of describing the emerging risks of biological invasions.
- Many futures thinking tools are available but are underutilised by biosecurity professionals.
- The value of each tool depends on the uncertainty, timeline, and audience for the information
- The term “Horizon Scanning” is widely used but most often inappropriately
- Most studies apply environmental scanning to identify near term species threats
- Environmental scanning doesn’t include a long-term perspective of change in drivers or policy
- More complex driver mapping (including interactions) is needed to set the context
- Horizon scanning approaches require a clear aim and target audience for findings
- The involvement of interdisciplinary, gender balanced teams is essential
- Roadmaps can be useful policy tools but the overarching goal or destination needs to be clear

Thank you

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HORIZON SCANNING ACTIVITY ON PLANT HEALTH IN EFSA

Sara Tramontini
EFSA Plant Health Monitoring Team

Magali Larenaudie
ANSES Plant Health Laboratory

Team Leader: **Sybre Vos**

What
EFSA Plant
Health
Monitoring Team
does

- Provides scientific advice and supports for EU risk managers on existing and emerging pests that threaten the EU agriculture and environment. Contributes to independent, timely risk communication
- Promotes scientific cooperation

Director : Philippe Reignault
Head of risk assesment unit : Emmanuel Gachet

What the Plant Health lab of ANSES does

- Reference, scientific and technical support body for plant health risks.
 - ID of phytopathogenic pathogens
 - Detection of GMOs
 - Expertise on invasive plants
 - Pest and pathogen ID
- Reference, research, monitoring, epidemiology, sci and technical expertise
- Partnerships for development of research activities

HORIZON SCANNING MAIN SCOPE

DG SANTE Mandate (Dec. 2016, 2017-2020) – current mandate (Jan 2021, 2021-2026)

EU regulatory framework for Plant Health: Reg. (EU) 2016/2031 into force from 14/12/2019

Known pests:
regulated pests (quarantine pests, priority pests, emergency measures), EPPO listed pests.

Non-listed pests: new species, non-regulated, non-listed pests, unknown pests.

HORIZON SCANNING IN A GLANCE

What if the pest is "non-listed"?

- New pest species in the newsletter because...
 - Outbreaks
 - Spreading
 - New host
 - New taxon

- Species added to HS tool
- Item added to the Newsletter

- Is it suitable for the PeMoScreening?

Newsletter workflow

- Continuous screening and selection of items
- Monthly meeting with scientific experts to:
 - Validate the newsletter content
 - Conduct PeMoScreening on a selected number of pests
- Newsletter finalisation
 - **30-40** items
 - **3-7** PeMo
- Sharing with EU Commission and PAFF
- Publication on open access EFSA Journal
- Communication via X (@Plants_EFSA) and Dashboard

Newsletter structure

1. Table of content
2. Introduction
3. Summary table
4. Main issues
5. Selected items with links

Pest	Hosts	Host range	Damage	EU distribution	Regulatory status	Topic
<i>Acanalonia conica</i> ▲	Morus, Prunus, Ulmus	Ulmaceae, Moraceae, Rosaceae, Solanaceae, Betulaceae, Vitaceae	Feeding damage, high honeydew production which leads to sooty mould	✓ AT, CH, CS, FR, HU, IT, RO, SI	Not listed	First finding
<i>Aculops cannabicolus</i> ▲	Hemp	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Curling of leaf edges, followed by leaf russetting and eventually, plant stunting.	✓ HU, PO	Not listed	First finding
<i>Bactrocera dorsalis</i>	Wide range of fruit and vegetable plants	Gentianaceae, Moraceae, Juglandaceae, Sapindaceae, Rosaceae...	Black or brown lesions on fruits, internal feeding of larvae, premature drop	✗ Under official control in FR, IT	Priority pest	New finding Management

3.

Acanalonia conica
 Authority: (Say)
 Insecta, Hemiptera, Fulgoromorpha, Acanaloniidae
 ▲ Positive PeMoScoring

■ First finding (BE)
 Nieuw uitheems insect ontdekt in Vlaanderen
New alien insect discovered in Flanders
 Nieuwsblad 24.Oct.2022
 In Schelle is vorige week dinsdag een nieuwe uitheemse gifgroene cicade, de '*Acanalonia conica*', ontdekt dankzij een waarneming van een burger. Dat meldt Natuurpunt.[\(more\)](#)

5. Last Tuesday, a new exotic green cicada, the '*Acanalonia conica*', was discovered in Schelle thanks to a sighting of a citizen. This was reported by Natuurpunt

Acanalonia conica

▲ Positive PeMoScoring

Acanalonia conica is a polyphagous insect not listed in any EU legal acts or EPPO lists. This newsletter includes a media article reporting a first finding in Belgium. The pest, which originates from North America, was detected by citizen science. The planthopper has been previously detected in other European countries such as France, Italy and Austria.

Acanalonia conica is a pest of plants in the Solanaceae, Rosaceae, Chenopodiaceae, Cornaceae, Cannabaceae, Vitaceae, Asteraceae and Scrophulariaceae families. The most relevant cultivated host plants are *Vitis vinifera* and *Corylus avellana*. The pest was included in the PeMoScoring screening and scored positive.

4. All the articles on *Acanalonia conica* are available on the webpage of [MEDISYS EFSA Plant Health](#).

PeMoScreening: 15 criteria

GO

No	Criterion
1	Host plants
2	Trade-related pathways
3	Difficulty of visual detection during inspection
4	Presence of the pest in the PRA area
5	Need of vectors
6	Entry by natural means
7	Climate suitability
8	Cultivated host plant distribution in PRA area
9	Host plants area
10	Non-cultivated host plants
11	Spread by natural means
12	Spread by human assistance
13	Yield losses
14	Plant death
15	Pest control measures

Threat

STOP

What if...

PeMo

+

Added to HS
tool and
monitored

- Main issue in the newsletter

- Discussion at PAFF

- Potential mandate for a pest categorisation

2017-2019:

63 pests PeMo scored
→ 19 PeMo- / 44 PeMo+ →
31 pests categorisations

PeMo-

PeMo results

2017-now:
207 pests screened

97 PeMo- / 110 PeMo+

37 Fungi,
37 Insects,
21 Viruses,
7 Bacteria,
7 Nematodes,
1 Mollusc

EFSA work on *Spodoptera frugiperda*

Tools

PHoRiS	Dashboard
For internal use with WG members (experts)	Free-access from EFSA website
https://r4eu.efsa.europa.eu/app/horizon-scanning	https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/powerbi/plant-health-horizon-scanning-dashboard
Scope: analysis	Scope: communication
2 sections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter editing • PeMoScreening 	3 sections: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emerging pests • Priority pests • Search engine
Section 2 to become accessible to externals possibly by the end of the year	New version to be delivered within 3 months

PHoRiS

PeMoScore for a new pest

Menu

Define new pest

[Host range](#)

Entry criteria

Establishment criteria

Spread criteria

Impact criteria

Results

Host range

Range of pest host plants

Host plants belong to more than 10 families

Host information

Scientific name	Family	Common name	Reference
<input type="text" value="Aa achalensis"/>	<input type="text" value="Orchidaceae"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Note: to remove rows, select the rows that need to be removed and right click on the table to display the table options. To change text in the table cells, double click on the cell.

	Scientific name	Family	Common name	Reference
1	Daucus carota f. carota	Apiaceae		
2	Pastinaca sativa	Apiaceae		
3	Lactuca sativa	Asteraceae	Lettuce	
4	Brassica napus	Brassicaceae		
5	Beta vulgaris	Amaranthaceae	Beet	
6	Spinacia oleracea	Amaranthaceae	Spinach	
7	Cucurbita moschata	Cucurbitaceae		
8	Cucumis sativus	Cucurbitaceae	Cucumber	
9	Dioscorea batatas			
10	Glycine max	Fabaceae	Soybean	

Showing page 1 of 3 entries

1 2 3

PHoRiS

Pest Horizon and Risk Scanning

v 0.0.33 - Report new issue
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1006271

Info PeMoScoring Newsletter Admin

Article Information

Column visibility Show All entries

Showing 1 to 39 of 39 entries Previous 1 Next

id	Vote	User vote	Article Status	Main issue (user)	Pest Name	Pest Group	Subtitle	Link	Description	Author	Edit
3	<input type="button" value="Vote"/>	No vote	Draft	No	Tomato leaf curl Karnataka virus	Viruses, viroids and phytoplasmas	Regulated pests - Quarantine pests - AnnexIA	Biological and molecular characterization of begomovirus and its DNA satellites associated with leaf curl disease of zinnia in India	tomato leaf curl Karnataka virus (ToLCKV) is a Begomovirus transmitted by the whitefly Bemisia tabacci. The article extends the know natural host range of this virus by reporting its discovery associated with a range of alpha- and beta-satellites in symptomatic Zinnia (Z. elegans) in India	Thierry	<input type="button" value="Edit"/>
4	<input type="button" value="Vote"/>	No vote	Draft	No	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus	Virus, viroids and phytoplasmas	Regulated pests - Other EU legal acts - Emergency control measures	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus associated with leaf mosaic, mottling and brown rugose patches on fruits of tomato in India	The article reports the first finding of the merging Tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus in symptomatic tomatoes in the states of Karnataka and Maharashtra in India.	Thierry	<input type="button" value="Edit"/>

Dashboard : How to inform about HS?

Emerging Pests

Insect pests and fungal pathogens may be harmless in their place of origin but very damaging when introduced in other regions, such as chestnut blight and ash dieback or Asian long-horned beetle in Europe. Due to global trade and environmental stresses including climate change, an increasing number of species can establish themselves and pose significant threats to European forest ecosystems, causing economic and environmental losses.

This dashboard includes the latest data and information updates as of 30 May 2023

Click on any of the dots on the map to view additional information about the pest in that location

Location	Title	Summary
-	-	-

- Interactive
- Self-explanatory
- Regularly updated
- Focused on a limited number of aspects
 - 3 sections

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/powerbi/plant-health-horizon-scanning-dashboard>

Emerging pests

- Pest not regulated neither suggested for regulation in the EU
- Selection triggered by
 - Outbreaks
 - New hosts
 - New type/level of damages
 - New taxa
- Manual feeding of the page (at least once/month)

In the dashboard:

- Identity of the pest
- Location(s) of the event(s)
- Title of the item triggering the news
- Short summary on the relevance of the news
- Active link to the original source
- Result of PeMo (when available)

Priority pests

Click on any of the buttons below to filter the line chart to show data only for the selected pest

- Agrilus anxius
- Agrilus planipennis
- Anastrepha ludens
- Anoplophora chinensis
- Anoplophora glabripennis
- Anthonomus eugeni
- Aromia bungii
- Bactericera cockerelli
- Bactrocera dorsalis
- Bactrocera zonata
- Bursaphelenchus xylophilus
- Candidatus Liberibacter spp.
- Conotrachelus nenuphar
- Dendrolimus sibiricus
- Phyllosticta citricarpa
- Popillia japonica
- Rhagoletis pomonella
- Spodoptera frugiperda
- Thaumetobia leucocetra
- Xylella fastidiosa

Priority Pests

The European Commission has published a list of 20 "priority pests" that present the most serious economic, environmental, and social threat to EU countries. The list includes Xylella fastidiosa, the Japanese beetle, the Asian long-horned beetle, citrus greening/dotydim black spot. The pests have been ranked on the basis of impact assessments carried out by EFSA and the Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC). You can find out more about EFSA's work on the project by reading our FAQ.

🕒 You can filter the line chart below to show data only for a specific time period using the slider.

Trends of pest reports in news items
Currently showing data for all priority pests

- 20 EU Priority Pests
- Amount of traffic of items identified on Medisys
- Automatic continuous feeding from the tool

- In the dashboard:
- Select pest
 - Select time period

Search engine

- All mentions of each single pest since the beginning of the project
- Selection triggered by
 - Taxonomic category according to legislation
 - Family and species
 - Results of PeMo
- Updated each time a new newsletter is published (once/month)

In the dashboard:

- Active link to the corresponding newsletter

EFSA newsletters

Following a request from the European Commission, EFSA publishes monthly newsletters collecting and summarizing the main news retrieved through the MedSys platform of JRC. All the newsletters are published on the EFSA Journal and stored in the dedicated virtual issue <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2903/J10.2903/J1831-4732>. The below search engine was conceived to facilitate the retrieval of specific published items.

Apply one or multiple filters to view the newsletters matching your selection.

Category: Search [Insects and Mites]

Family: Search [Curculionidae]

Species: Search [Xylosandrus co...]

PeMo results: Search [Positive]

Currently showing 8 newsletters matching the applied filter(s)

You have selected specie(s) with positive PeMo result

Species	Newsletters	Month	Link
Xylosandrus compactus	Media Monitoring	October 2021	🔗
Xylosandrus compactus	Scientific Literature Monitoring	June 2021	🔗
Xylosandrus compactus	Media Monitoring	February 2021	🔗
Xylosandrus compactus	Scientific Literature Monitoring	May 2020	🔗
Xylosandrus compactus	Media Monitoring	February 2020	🔗
Xylosandrus compactus	Media Monitoring	May 2019	🔗

HORIZON SCANNING: EVOLUTION

EIOS EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE FROM OPEN SOURCES

Collaboration with other institutions

Open dashboards
 European Commission
 JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE

HORIZON SCANNING: EVOLUTION

21

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

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Questions?

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CONTACT US
efsa.europa.eu/en/contact/askefsa

Results: from horizon scanning to pest categorisation

2017-2019: 63 pests PeMo scored => 19 PeMo- / 44 PeMo+

Mandated pest categorization March
21: 31 pests PeMo+

published on the
EFSA journal

Sustainable plant production based on insight from One Health: what will be the scope and targets for horizon scanning?

Cindy E. Morris

Plant Pathology Research Unit, INRAE @ Avignon

cindy.morris@inrae.fr

EFSA/ANSES workshop, Horizon Scanning for Plant Health, 9-10 April 2024, Maisons-Alfort, FR

How is One Health related to horizon scanning?

One Health: a concept about the interdependence of the health of all organisms through natural ecological processes and via human activities, exploitation of planetary resources, trade, transportation, etc.

Horizon scanning: foreseeing the upcoming risks (to plant health, for example)

One Health

Identify connections. Set up actions and policies to disrupt deleterious connections and foster beneficial connections

Horizon scanning

Forecast dangers. Formulate advice for actions and policies.

Most epidemiological forecasting for risks to plant health is oriented around 4 spatio-temporal axes

Examples

The spatial-temporal horizon for forecasting risks could be expanded with 4 additional axes

The BEYOND project PPR CPA
<https://beyond.paca.hub.inrae.fr/>

Examples

Insight from a One Health analytical perspective
→ elucidate new forecasting indicators

Overcome missing or poorly-developed concepts in plant disease epidemiology and management that could lead to new indicators for forecasting

1. Reservoirs outside of agriculture, and on substrates other than plants
2. Virulence factors can also be adaptations for survival in the environment
3. Framework for assessing potential risk of microbial lines before they emerge as pathogens
4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

1. Reservoirs of plant pathogens outside of agriculture

Pathogen life cycles are often incomplete stories of life histories

One Health perspective → new habitats and substrates to survey

1. Reservoirs of plant pathogens outside of agriculture

When we look elsewhere – we can find plant pathogens

The case of *Pseudomonas syringae*

Known

Discovered – when we looked

1. Reservoirs of plant pathogens outside of agriculture

Potential pathogens are everywhere

plants tested

cantaloupe

beet

lettuce

Substrates that harbor pathogenic *P. syringae*

- Environment
 - Wild alpine plants
 - Leaf litter
 - Snow pack
 - Streams, lakes, rivers
 - Ground water
 - Cloud water
- Agric.
 - Irrigation water basins
 - Crop plants

Genetic diversity in the environment ≥ in agriculture

Crop & environ'l strains are indistinguishable

Genealogies inferred by ClonalFrame for strains in clade 2d from crops and the environment (2293 common genes)

1. Reservoirs of plant pathogens outside of agriculture

One Health perspective → survey (unsuspected?) non agricultural reservoirs

Survey water, precipitation, wild and feral plants – for various pathogens

Pseudomonas syringae

soft rot *Pectobacteriaceae* Ben Moussa et al. 2022. *Phytopathology* 112:1676-1685.

Botrytis cinerea Bardin et al 2018. *Frontier in Plant Sci* doi 10:3389/FPS.2018.01820 .

Fusarium graminearum Fulcher et al. 2019. *Phytopathology* 109:2124-2131.

Venturia inaequalis Lemaire et al 2016. *New Phytologist* 209:1220-1229.

Phytoplasmas Trivellone et al 2021. *Ecol & Evol.* 11:6493–6503.

2. Virulence factors can also be adaptations for survival in the environment

Human/animal pathogens have numerous dual use factors for virulence and environmental fitness (melanins, efflux pumps, EPS, etc). Little known for plant pathogens

Some examples from fungi causing *Septoria* diseases of wheat

Zymoseptoria tritici effector Zt6 = **phytotoxic ribonuclease**,
broad spectrum microbial toxicity; niche protection
Liu et al. 2016. *New Phytologist* 211:1052-1064

Parastagonospora nodorum effector SnTox1 induces cell wall death of wheat;
protects hyphae from digestion by chitinases of plants & mycoparasites
Kettles et al. 2018. *New Phytologist* 217:320-331

Overall

Effector repertoires of non-symbiotic saprophytic fungi are indistinguishable from their symbiotic relatives.
Effectors are probably a means for fungi to manipulate their environment – and not simply plant hosts

Sneliders et al 2022 *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, 46:5 <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsre/fuac022>

3. Framework for assessing potential risk of microbial lines before they emerge as pathogens

For 12 combinations of plant pathogens x cultivars within a host species

- *P. syringae* x apricot
- *Puccinia hordei* x barley
- *Venturia inaequalis* x apple
- *Podosphaera xanthi* x melon
- *Botrytis cinerea* x tomato
- *Zymoseptoria tritici* x wheat
- *Phytophthora capsici* x pepper
- *Aphanomyces euteiches* x pea
- *Plasmopara viticola* x grapevine
- *Aphis gossypii* x melon
- *Globodera pallida* x potato
- Potato virus Y x pepper

Host range is an overlapping continuum
with very few distinct "pathotypes"

Moury et al. 2021. *Peer Community Journal*, 1: e44. doi : 10.24072/pcjournal.51. <https://peercommunityjournal.org/articles/10.24072/pcjournal.51/>

3. Framework for assessing potential risk of microbial lines before they emerge as pathogens

One Health perspective

→ indicators of the presence of potential pathogens in environments and substrates with increasing contact with agriculture

Much, much more research is needed

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

In addition to quarantine surveillance at borders:

Can we predict or strategically survey long distance dissemination by wind, precipitation and surface waters?

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

Develop approaches to strategically survey long distance dissemination by wind, precipitation and surface waters

Approach #1

Map what can be observed directly

- pathogens in waterways

Infer movement of pathogens when direct observation is impossible or impractical

- pathogens/vectors in the atmosphere

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

Durance River basin

southeastern France

21 sites

4 seasons / 2 years

source to sink (300 km)

- *Pseudomonas syringae*
- Soft Rot enteric bacteria

Morris et al. 2022. *bioRxiv* 2022.09.06.506731;
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2022.09.06.506731>

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

One Health perspective for sporadically-occurring pathogens
→ indicators of sources for spill-over into rivers

One Health perspective for ubiquitous pathogens
→ indicators of environmental conditions/services that allow for survival and dissemination in rivers without disease causation

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

Develop approaches to strategically survey long distance dissemination by wind, precipitation and surface waters

Approach #2

Map what can be observed directly - *pathogens in waterways*

Infer movement of pathogens when direct observation is impossible or impractical

 - *pathogens/vectors in the atmosphere*

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

Strategy

1. Map the trajectories and characterize their dynamics.
2. Calculate the intensity of connectedness with potential source and across the trajectory.

The tropolink web app

<https://tropolink.fr/>

Air mass trajectories
across time and space

Connectivity matrix &
Weighted oriented network

CODE	Carpentras	Manoque	Sisteron	Saint-Andre-les-Alpes	Gap	Biancon	Mont_Vivo
CODE	Carpentras	10	1	0	0	0	0
Manoque	4	10	7	0	2	0	0
Sisteron	2	3	10	1	9	0	0
Saint-Andre-les-Alpes	1	1	5	10	6	4	2
Gap	1	0	3	2	10	0	0
Biancon	0	0	1	2	3	10	1
Mont_Vivo	0	1	2	2	3	10	10

4. Spill-over via natural processes that disseminate constantly and at long distances

One Health perspective

→ *Advice for positioning surveillance in time and space to maximize possibility to detect pathogens/pests incoming with wind*

→ *Information and strategy for finding sources of wind-borne pathogens*

Comprehensive, One Health surveillance for human, animal and plant health have common needs

→ *multidisciplinary approaches to filling knowledge gaps toward*

Morris et al. 2022. *Plant Pathol.* 71, 86–97

A One Health analytical perspective can enhance sustainability of agriculture

→ Back to the future

Although the modern One Health movement started formally in ~2004 by the medical and veterinary communities, the “oneness” of the health of all organisms was recognized by crop production and soil specialists since the early 1900’s

- The soil is an organism – Rudolph Steiner, 1924
- The farm is an organism - Walter J. Northbourne, 1940
- Soil life is a “living bridge” that supports the health of plants, livestock and humans – Albert Howard, 1943
- The health of soil, plant, animal and man is one and indivisible – Eve Balfour, the Soil Society, 1946
- Agroecological concepts and practices including organic agriculture

Declaration of the IFOAM: “organic agriculture should sustain and enhance the health of soil, plant, animal, human and planet as one and indivisible”

Soil is recognized as a central hub of plant, animal and human health

Banerjee & van de Heijden 2023. Nature Rev. Microbiol. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-022-00779-w>

Functions of soil borne microorganisms – **that can be managed via soil quality**

Organic matter is key to assuring the ecosystem services of soil microbial communities

Modern agricultural practices have robbed soil of organic matter.

Morris et al.
CABI Reviews (2024) 19:1
<https://doi.org/10.1079/cabireviews.2024.0008>

 CABI Reviews

REVIEW

More than food: Why restoring the cycle of organic matter in sustainable plant production is essential for the One Health nexus

Cindy E. Morris^{1*}, Andrea Radici², Christine N. Meynard³, Nicolas Sauvion⁴, Claire Nedellec⁵, Ghislain Geniaux⁶ and Samuel Soubeyrand²

<https://doi.org/10.1079/cabireviews.2024.0008>

→ indicators of ecosystem services that foster plant, animal and human health

→ policies and governance that give key roles to plant health managers in assuring One Health

A One Health analytical perspective can enhance sustainability of agriculture

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2018 - 2021

SPREE: Strategic preemptive pathogen surveillance of air and water to anticipate plant disease emergence in scenarios of changing land use

2021 - 2026

BEYOND: Building epidemiological surveillance and prophylaxis with observations both near and distant <https://beyond.paca.hub.inrae.fr/>

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BEYOND Assemblée Générale
8-10 Nov. 2022
Avignon

On the horizon: Identifying invasive species threats in the United States

Susan Canavan

Deah Lieurance

Amy Kendig

Wesley M Daniel

Funded by

Collaborators

Working group

Working group

Objectives

- Provide ranked list of invasive species
- Identify pathways for arrival
- Categorize impacts & impact mechanisms

Build a list for consideration – start big and narrow

CABI Horizon Scanning Tool
Prioritizing invasive species threats

Area at risk: USA/Florida Start Scan

I am only interested in plant pests

Refine by: Results: 9637 species found Save and share scan Download as CSV

Source countries	Pathways	Plant hosts	Plant parts in trade	Habitats	Taxonomic group
		Abacarus hystrix			Invertebrates
		Abacarus kőrőscsomai			Invertebrates
		Abbottina rivularis	Chinese false gudgeon		Vertebrates
		Abelmoschus moschatus	musk mallow		Plants
		Ablattaria laevigata			Invertebrates
		Abraaxas grossulariata moth	common magpie		Invertebrates
		Abutilon grandifolium	hairy indian mallow		Plants
		Abutilon indicum	country mallow		Plants
		Abutilon mosaic virus			Viruses

Current search:

- Neighbouring countries: USA/Alabama, USA/Georgia
- Matching Continents (479): Africa (65)
- Africa: Aldabra, Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Bouvet Island, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon
- Show more
- Pathways
- Plant hosts
- Plant parts in trade
- Habitats
- Taxonomic group

9629 species

Divide into taxonomic groups

CABI Horizon Scanning Tool
Prioritizing invasive species threats

Area at risk: USA/Florida I am only interested in plant pests **Start Scan**

Results: 9637 species found **Save and share scan** [Download as CSV](#)

Refine by:	Preferred scientific name	International common name	Taxonomic group	View datasheet
source countries				
Pathways				
Plant hosts	Abacarus hystrix	grain rust mite	Invertebrates	CPC (Basic)?
Plant parts in trade				
Habitats	Abacarus kőrőscsomai		Invertebrates	CPC (Basic)?
Taxonomic group	Abbottina rivularis	Chinese false gudgeon	Vertebrates	ISC (Full)
	Abelmoschus moschatus	musk mallow	Plants	CPC (Full)
	Ablattaria laevigata		Invertebrates	ISC (Full)
	Abraxas grossulariata	common magpie moth	Invertebrates	ISC (Basic)?
	Abutilon grandifolium	hairy indian mallow	Plants	CPC (Basic)?
	Abutilon indicum	country mallow	Plants	ISC (Full)
	Abutilon mosaic virus		Viruses	ISC (Full)
				CPC (Basic)?

Current search:

- Neighbouring countries: USA/Alabama, USA/Georgia
- Matching Continents (479): Africa (65), Aldabra, Algeria, Angola, Benin, Botswana, Bouvet Island, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon
- Show more
- Pathways
- Plant hosts
- Plants parts in trade
- Habitats
- Taxonomic group

7177 species

Divide into taxonomic groups

Divide into taxonomic groups

ECOSPHERE
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ARTICLE |

Identifying invasive species threats, pathways, and impacts to improve biosecurity

Deah Lieurance Susan Canavan, Donald C. Behringer, Amy E. Kendig, Carey R. Minter, Lindsey S. Reisinger, Christina M. Romagosa, S. Luke Flory, Julie L. Lockwood ... [See all authors](#) ▾

First published: 14 December 2023 | <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecs2.4711>

Handling Editor: Hunter S. Lenihan

Divide into taxonomic groups

ECOSPHERE
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RESEARCH ARTICLE

 NeoBiota
A peer-reviewed open-access journal
Advancing research on alien species and biological invasions

Scanning the horizon for invasive plant threats using a data-driven approach

Amy E. Kendig^{1*}, Susan Canavan^{1,2*}, Patti J. Anderson³, S. Luke Flory¹,
Lyn A. Gettys⁴, Doria R. Gordon^{5,6}, Basil V. Iannone III⁷, John M. Kunzer⁸,
Tabitha Petri⁹, Ian A. Pfingsten¹⁰, Deah Lieurance¹

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

data	description
cab_list_full.csv	list of potential invasive species to Florida generated by CABI Horizon Scan Tool on November 15, 2019
GCW_full_list_020420.csv	Global Compendium of Weeds downloaded on February 4, 2020
PlantAtlasDataExport-20191211-194219.csv	Atlas of Florida plants downloaded December 11, 2019
Taxon_x_List_GloNAF_vanKleunenetal2018Ecology_121119.csv	GloNAF 1.2 database downloaded December 11, 2019
the-plant-list	The Plant List Database downloaded August 3, 2021

code	description
gcw_processing.R	R script to format data downloaded from the Global Compendium of Weeds
native_introduced_ranges.R	R script to create map of native and introduced ranges of taxa on the final list
random_draws_plant_families.R	R script to evaluate over- and underrepresentation of plant families in initial and final list
review_process_comparison.R	R script to evaluate differences in scores before and after peer-review and consensus-building
scores_certainty_pathways.R	R script to create figures of scores, certainty, and pathways for final list
risk_scores_analys.R	R script to evaluate final risk scores
pathways_process.R	R script to process pathways to introduction data
taxa_list_processing.R	R script to create list used for rapid risk assessments from an initial list

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS)

Taxonomic Name Resolution Service

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

4817 taxa known to occur in Florida (native or naturalized).

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

Federal Noxious Weed List

Florida Invasive Species Council List

Florida Noxious Weed list

Florida Prohibited Aquatic Plants List

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

13,083 taxa naturalized anywhere outside of their native range

A GLOBAL
COMPENDIUM

of WEEDS

THIRD EDITION

R. P. Randall

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

- data included from over 50,000 databases
- 100 (12%) most common taxa

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

2. Rapid risk assessment

Pathways for arrival: Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) pathways categorization

The process – Plant group

1. Data-based list processing

2. Rapid risk assessment

3. Review and consensus building

Results

Plant Group

High Risk

Results

Plant Group

Results

Plant Group

Results

All Taxonomic Groups

Policy and implementation

- Recommendation full risk analysis of high risk species
- Subset of the Florida scan has been vetted as a prevention list for the Everglades Restoration Task force (multi-agency; part of the water resources development act)
- Big scans are getting implemented in the National Early Detection and Rapid Response (EDRR) Framework – 50 state plus territories

**ASSESSMENT OF
NON-NATIVE PLANTS**

Ongoing and upcoming Horizon scans

Ongoing and upcoming Horizon scans

1. Global horizon scan to assess U.S. invasion risk of terrestrial and freshwater vertebrates in trade [in review] led by W.M. Daniel, H.R. Sofaer, C.S. Jarnevich

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3. Horizon Scan to identify range shifting forest pests in future climate conditions (25 years)

Ongoing and upcoming Horizon scans

1. National horizon scan to assess U.S. invasion risk of terrestrial and freshwater vertebrates in trade [in review] *led by W.M. Daniel, H.R. Sofaer, C.S. Jarnevich*

2. A Horizon Scan to collaboratively identify invasive species threats to the islands of Puerto Rico and the U.S. Virgin Islands *led by D. Lieurance*

3. Horizon Scan to identify range shifting forest pests in future climate conditions (25 years)

4. National horizon scan of plants in trade in the United States - *led by D. Lieurance*

Using tools from culturomics and iEcology

Using tools from culturomics and iEcology

- Conservation culturomics: Computational lexicology that studies human behaviour and cultural trends through the quantitative analysis of digitized texts, images, videos, sounds etc. (Ladle et al. 2016)
- iEcology: The study of ecological patterns and processes using data generated for other purposes and stored digitally (Jarić et al. 2020).

Ladle, Richard J., et al. "Conservation culturomics." *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 14.5 (2016): 269-275.

Jarić, Ivan, et al. "iEcology: harnessing large online resources to generate ecological insights." *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 35.7 (2020): 630-639.

Using digital data

Twitter,
Instagram, Wikipedia,
YouTube, TikTok,
Google Trends

Using digital data

Twitter,
Instagram, Wikipedia,
YouTube, TikTok,
Google Trends

API
Access

Using digital data

Shaindel Beers 🍷 @shaindelr · Aug 29

Let's play **invasive species** you hate. I'll go first -- tree of heaven.

💬 102 🔄 14 ❤️ 170 📤

Using digital data

Let's play **invasive species** you hate. I'll go first -- tree of heaven.

```
texts_clean <- texts %>%
  iconv(to = "ASCII", sub = " ") %>%
  str_replace_all("http[s]*[-:~&#./[:alnum:]]*", "") %>% ### remove hyperlinks
  str_replace_all("non-native", "nonnative") %>%
  str_replace_all("butter fly", "butterfly") %>%
  str_replace_all("butter[ ]*flies", "butterfly") %>% ### modified this
  str_replace_all("crazi ant", "crazy ant") %>%
  str_replace_all("lantern fly", "lanternfly") %>%
  replace_contraction() %>%
  str_replace_all("#[:alnum:]+", "") %>% # remove hashtags
  str_replace_all("@[:alnum:]+", "") %>% # remove tags
  str_replace_all("&[#]*[:alnum:]+;", "") %>% ### remove html_characters
  str_replace_all("(RT|via)((?:\\b\\W*@[\\w+]+)", "") %>%
  str_replace_all("[[:punct:]]", " ") %>% # remove punctuation
  str_replace_all("[0-9]+", " ") %>% # remove numbers
  str_replace_all("[\\t]{2,}", " ") %>% # convert tabs to spaces
  str_replace_all("\\n", " ") %>% # convert new lines to spaces
  str_squish() %>% # remove leading, lagging and double spaces
  replace_symbol() %>%
  replace_kern() %>%
  str_to_lower() %>% # convert to lower
  lemmatize_strings()
```

Using digital data

Let's play **invasive species** you hate. I'll go first -- tree of heaven.

let us play invasive species you hate I will go first tree of heaven

```

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```

Using digital data

Using digital data

Using digital data

Using digital data

tweets n = 37052 retweets n = 58680 likes n = 234984 replies n = 14204

- taxa group
- invert
 - fish
 - herp
 - mammal
 - plant

- Statistical analysis
- Temporal and trend analysis
- Sentiment analysis
- Content analysis
- Geographical variation

Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

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Using digital data

Statistical analysis

Temporal and trend analysis

Sentiment analysis

Content analysis

Geographical variation

Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

Mystery seeds: Amazon bans foreign plant sales in US

© 6 September 2020

- Now only sale of seeds by sellers based in the US

Statistical analysis

Temporal and trend analysis

Sentiment analysis

Content analysis

Geographical variation

Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

- Statistical analysis
- Temporal and trend analysis
- Sentiment analysis
- Content analysis**
- Geographical variation

Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

- Statistical analysis
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Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

Statistical analysis

Temporal and trend analysis

Sentiment analysis

Content analysis

Geographical variation

Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

Before extinction

After extinction

Statistical analysis

Temporal and trend analysis

Sentiment analysis

Content analysis

Geographical variation

Provide metrics on societal interest and engagement on a topic.

Using digital data

Conclusions

- HS growing in popularity for use with invasive species
 - Implement it with other aspects of biosecurity and invasion ecology
 - Made possible by free and accessible global databases e.g., CABI ISC, GloNAF, GBIF
- Iterative process
 - New technology e.g., culturomics and iEcology
 - Try to incorporate trade, cultural trends, human dimensions
 - Improve automation
 - Implementing within national scan and PR/USVI scan

Health emergencies throughout the year and on every continent
 local – national – regional - global

WHO Hub for Pandemic and Epidemic Intelligence - Portfolio

Connect

Convene partners to prioritize & transform collaborative surveillance efforts

Innovate

Innovate effective solutions to solve key surveillance challenges

Strengthen

Scale up the most successful solutions to surveillance barrier

EIOS

EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE FROM OPEN SOURCES

WHAT

prevent and mitigate public health emergencies

HOW

connect experts and data around the world and provide training and tools to rapidly detect, contextualise, analyse, assess and share information.

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THE EIOS INITIATIVE IS BUILT ON THREE PILLARS

Collaboration

Community

Technology

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FROM OPEN SOURCES

Public health surveillance / intelligence prepare - prevent - detect - assess - respond

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EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

The EIOS system

EIOS
EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

All Hazards - One Health

Fit-for-purpose,
constantly evolving
web-based system
designed to
augment and
accelerate global
public health
intelligence activities

- EIOS core system developed by the Joint Research Center of the European Commission (JRC)
- Additional **modules** developed by multiple partners
- The **processing chain** harvests articles from the set of selected sources
- Classifies articles with **relevant categories for public health** + adds other metadata + detects duplicates
- Sends enriched information to the EIOS portal

Broad range of sources

EIOS
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

EIOS
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

Innovating and integrating Open Source Public Health Intelligence through community and technology

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EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

A GLOBAL INITIATIVE LED BY THE
WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION

Snapshot of EIOS System

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FROM OPEN SOURCES
World Health Organization | HUB

TIME PERIOD
Period: Entire Period

CATEGORIES
All WHO Categories (652 of 652)

MENTIONED GEOGRAPHICAL AREAS
Countries, territories and areas: No filter
Countries, territories and areas in Continents: No filter
Countries, territories and areas in WHO Regions: No filter

MENTIONED ENTITIES
Mentioned persons: No filter
Mentioned organisations and other entities: No filter

LANGUAGE
Article Language(s): No filter

SOURCES
Specific Source(s): No filter

CBRN	3.88M
Chemical	3.11M
Disasters	15M
Diseases From A-D	53.8M
Diseases From E-I	5.05M
Diseases From J-Q	3.38M
Diseases From R-Z	2.39M
Food Related	1.12M
Health Systems	861k
Immunity	9.26M
Mass Gathering	1.07M
Measures	6.17M
Outcomes	6.58M
Populations	3.2M
Product Safety	461k
Societal	1.32M
Symptoms	1.24M

Coronavirus	51.7M
Coronavirus Mutation E484k	8.64k
Coronavirus Mutation K417N	3.04k
Coronavirus mutation L452R	8.85k
Coronavirus Mutation N501Y	7.19k
Coronavirus Mutation P681H	1.08k
Coronavirus Variant A.23.1	1.48k
Coronavirus Variant Alpha	198k
Coronavirus Variant B.1.1.222	3.36k
Coronavirus Variant B.1.1.316	173
Coronavirus Variant B.1.1.318	1.18k
Coronavirus Variant B.1.1.2.5	68
Coronavirus Variant B.1.324.1	49
Coronavirus Variant B.1.616	1.54k
Coronavirus Variant B.1.617	120k
Coronavirus Variant Beta	116k
Coronavirus Variant Cluster-5	244
Coronavirus Variant Delta	486k
Coronavirus Variant Epsilon	8.23k
Coronavirus Variant Eta	3.39k
Coronavirus Variant Fin-796H	35
Coronavirus Variant Gamma	97.6k
Coronavirus Variant identified in Tunisia	825
Coronavirus Variant Iota	7.33k
Coronavirus Variant Kappa	4.12k
Coronavirus Variant Lambda	8.48k
Coronavirus Variant Mu	7.96k
Coronavirus Variant Omicron	471k
Coronavirus Variant Theta	5.36k
Coronavirus Variant Zeta	4.54k
Coronavirus Variants	2.19M

Plant Health Threats (Alphabetically)	11.4k
Plant Health Threats (Taxa)	1.2k
Actinobacteria	8
Agaricomycotina	0
Alphaproteobacteria	77
Angiospermae	1
Arachnida	0
Betaproteobacteria	50
Chromadorea	59
Chytridiomycetes	5
Dothideomycetes	19
Enoplea	0
Gammaproteobacteria	207
Gastropoda	13
Insecta	727
Leotiomycetes	1

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EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES
World Health Organization | HUB

EIOS - All Hazard, One Health Approach

Plant Health - important dimension

- Direct impact on human and animal health
- Carriers of human pathogens and harmful toxins
- Antimicrobial and antifungal resistance
- Food safety / security
- Displacement
- Agriculture / Environment
- Economy

The screenshot displays the EIOS web application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with options like 'Monitoring', 'Documents', 'Dashboards', 'Training', 'Communities and Teams', and 'Help and Feedback'. The user is logged in as 'Johannes Christof SCHNITZLER'. The main content area is titled 'Board: Spodoptera frugiperda - Famine'. On the left, there is a 'CATEGORIES' sidebar with a tree view showing 'All Plant Health Categories' (3 of 4855 selected), 'EU Legislation Pests' (1 of 2471 selected), 'Plant Health Threats (Taxa)' (1 of 722 selected), 'Insecta' (1 of 461 selected), 'Lepidoptera' (1 of 36 selected), and 'Noctuidae' (1 of 4 selected). The 'Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR]' category is selected. Below the sidebar, there is a 'MENTIONED GEOGRAPHICAL AREAS' section. The main board area shows a search bar with 'Any article' and 'Import Date' filters. Below the search bar, there is a 'TOTAL ARTICLES' section with a count of 1. The article title is 'Bugoma Forest Under Siege by Human Hands, Perpetuating Environmental Disaster' by 'watchdoguganda' on '03 Apr 13:16 UTC'. The article is in 'English'. Below the article title, there are several 'PIN TO RECENT BOARDS' buttons. The 'CATEGORIES' section below the article shows 'Deforestation', 'Drought', 'Ecology', 'Man-Made Disasters', 'Natural Disasters', and 'Spodoptera frugiperda [LAPHFR]'. The 'MENTIONED COUNTRIES, TERRITORIES AND AREAS' section shows 'Uganda'. The 'AUTOMATIC SUMMARY' section provides a brief overview of the article's content. The 'DESCRIPTION' section contains the full text of the article. The 'SEARCH HIGHLIGHTS' section shows the words 'army worms' and 'famine' highlighted in blue.

The EIOS initiative has been adopted by over 85 Member States and over 20 organisations and networks

EIOS Trainings

220
EIOS trainings

3500
Training participants

200
EIOS trained Member States/organisations

1900
Participants enrolled in the EIOS online OpenWHO course

EIOS Communities: Cumulative Growth

* Projected for 2024. All communities have received EIOS training, enabling them to effectively use the EIOS system. Communities can be Member States, regional CDCs, other organizations and networks.

EIOS
EPIDEMIOLOGICAL INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

Anomaly Detection

Anomaly detection

- Based on changes in geospatial time distribution
- NLP (lexical rules)
- ML methods
- Feedback loop

Advanced Analysis

Style and tone credibility (experimental)

Your opinion

How would you judge the credibility of this article, only based on style and tone, without verifying the facts?

Low credibility

Hard to say

High credibility

- AI/ML algorithms on EIOS data
- Credibility Assessment
- Recommender System
- Noise Reduction

EIOS
EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

For more
information

<http://www.who.int/eios>
eios@who.int

World Health
Organization

EIOS
EPIDEMIC INTELLIGENCE
FROM OPEN SOURCES

Analysis of Disinformation Narratives: Climate Change

Kristina Kovacikova, Bonka Kotseva, Nikolaos Nikolaidis,
Nicolo Faggiani, Irene Vianini, Jens Linge

10 April 2024

Mission

Support Commission services in the fight against disinformation through R&D and advanced tools, including detection and processing of disinformation, news monitoring, reporting, ad hoc analyses and providing inputs to policy.

Historical context / main themes

- Team was created in the run-up to the EP elections 2019
- COVID-19 since day 1 (31 December 2019):
 - Situational updates
 - Narratives monitoring
- Climate Change: side-events at both COP27 and COP28
- Russian military aggression against Ukraine
- Migration
- Israel/Gaza

3

Machine-learning for identification of most important narratives

Classification of texts:

- Detection of texts having **predefined property**: already known narrative, framing, persuasion techniques, ...

4

Multilingual clustering of texts:

- Cluster similar articles into **stories**
- LLMs for **keywords** extraction or **summarization**

Trend analysis of COVID-19 mis/disinformation narratives

- Daily and weekly briefs since the start of COVID-19
- Methodology:
 - Codebook of mis/disinfo narratives
 - Manual annotation of articles
 - AI for automatic classification of narratives

Supernarrative	Narrative 1	Narrative 2
Anti-minority narratives	Anti-immigrant narratives	Anti-Muslim narratives
Claims of authoritarianism and dystopia	Censorship by digital platforms	Turn to authoritarianism
Conspiracy theories	Coronavirus escaped from Wuhan lab	Coronavirus is a hoax, used to control the world
Criticism of EU and inter/national actors	Criticism of the EU	Criticism of national governments
Criticism of restrictions	Anti-lockdown narratives	Anti-mask narratives
Distrust towards media	Media	Fact checkers
Downplaying COVID-19	COVID-19 not more dangerous than flu	COVID-19 spread and/or deaths overestimated
Fearmongering	New variant(s)	New wave(s)
Geopolitics	Anti-China narratives	Pro-Russia narratives
Vaccine-related narratives	Anti-vax conspiracy theories	Anti-mandatory vaccination narratives

5 <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0291423>

Covid-19 related articles after March 2022

6

Russian military aggression against Ukraine: Supernarratives

7

Climate Change: narratives

8

Climate Change: narratives

9

Clustering to detect top stories for 'Species/plants /reefs aren't showing climate impacts'

- 1: Climate Change and its Impact on Biodiversity and Ecosystems
- 2: Impacts of Climate Change on Marine Ecosystems and Wildlife
- 3: "Threatened Extinction of Migratory Species: UN Report"
- 4: "Climate Change & Anthropocene Extinction: Impacts on Species Interactions and Adaptation"
- 5: "Globalists' Agenda: Promoting Cricket Consumption for Chitin's Parasitic Protection"
- 6: Unraveling the Mystery of Megalodon's Extinction
- 7: "Controversial Findings: Coral's Recovery Puts Science and Media under Scrutiny"
- 8: Climate Change Threats to European Ecosystems: Fire Ants and Bumblebees in Peril
- 9: "EU Approval of Insect Species as Human Food"
- 10: "India's Snow Leopard Population: A Scientific Survey Reveals 718 Strong"

10

Clustering to detect top stories for 'Species/plants /reefs aren't showing climate impacts'

2: Impacts of Climate Change on Marine Ecosystems and Wildlife

Texts classification – Persuasion Techniques, PT

- We perform automatic labelling of a set of 23 common Persuasion Techniques

Examples:

- **Slogans:** "Support the Farmers – they feed us all"
- **Name Calling-Labeling:** "The government should stop prosecuting peaceful protesters, and instead find ways to tackle the climate crisis."
- **Flag waving:** "And as America has always done, we will turn crisis into opportunity ..."

Persuasion techniques inside of 'Species/plants/reefs aren't showing climate impacts'

13

How do we use these results?

- Provide further insights for briefing material
- Analyse country trends
- Detect long-term trends
- Discover new/unexpected narratives from clustered articles
- Ad hoc analysis of any topic

14

Story: 0: "COP28: Global Climate Change Discussions and Actions"
 1: "Climate Change: Impacts on Health, Economy, and Global Security"
 2: "Greta Thunberg: Climate Activism, Controversies, and Arrests"
 3: "COP28: Global Climate Change Conference in Dubai"

Clustering o... communities_graph_th0_4_res1.0
 communities_graph_th0_5_res0.5
 communities_graph_th0_5_res1.0
 communities_graph_th0_6_res0.5
 communities_graph_th0_6_res1.0
 communities_graph_th0_75_res0.5

PT name: Appeal_to_Hypocrisy: 3837
 Appeal_to_Popularity: 137
 Appeal_to_Time: 210
 Appeal_to_Values: 1985
 Causal_Oversimplification: 579
 Consequential_Oversimplification: 91
 Conversation_Killer: 1952
 Doubt: 3939
 Exaggeration-Minimisation: 1500
 False_Dilemma-No_Choice: 637
 Flag_Waving: 282
 Guilt_by_Association: 989
 Loaded_Language: 3128
 Name_Calling-Labeling: 4493
 Obfuscation-Vagueness-Confusion: 165
 Questioning_the_Reputation: 2521
 Red_Herring: 293
 Repetition: 507
 Slogans: 4663
 Straw_Man: 1045
 Whataboutism: 58

0: Förra veckan dömdes Greta Thunberg till böter för ohörsamhet mot ordningsmakten efter en klimat...
 1: "Fără ambasadă evrească pe pământ arabi!"
 2: Environmental group Greenpeace said two of its activists scaled the Intercontinental Hotel in May
 3: Hier sehen Sie den Beitrag von Greta Thunberg.
 4: In einem Beitrag heißt es » Free Palestine from the river to the sea.«
 5: Video footage showed Thunberg, wearing a badge with the slogan "Oil Money Out" standing call...
 6: t muss ihre Stimme erheben und einen sofortigen Waffenstillstand, Gerechtigkeit und Freiheit für...
 7: „Stop Financing Fossil Fuels“, was auf Deutsch in etwa übersetzt in etwa:
 8: Fossil Free London activists banged drums and chanted "oil, oil money, out, out, out" as they bl...
 9: (Kiemelt képpönként Greta Thunberg svéd klímaaktivista reagál, amikor egy rendőrségi furgon felé...
 10: Auf Plakaten stand zum Beispiel „Make Polluters Pay“ (übersetzt etwa:
 11: *) Sie spielte damit offenkundig auf die von Israel besetzten palästinensischen Gebiete an.
 12: *) Sie spielte damit offenkundig auf die von Israel besetzten palästinensischen Gebiete an.
 13: Thunberg was among dozens of protesters who chanted oil money out and attempted to block...
 14: Several hundred protesters gathered by the InterContinental London Park Lane hotel during the...
 15: Thunberg war zuletzt auch wegen ihrer Position im Nahostkonflikt in die Diskussion geraten.
 16: Outside the forum, demonstrators banged drums and chanted "stop the oil, stop the gas" and "A...
 17: oft banners and chanted "oil money out" and "cancel the conference," while some lit yellow and...
 18: „No climate justice on occupied land.“

Article Snippet	count
"y "Esta judía está con Palestina".	10
Kurz darauf postete sie ein Foto von sich selbst, auf dem sie ein Schild mit der Aufschrift „Stand with Gaza“ hält, begleitet von einem Text, der zum globalen Streik in Solidarität mit Palästina und Gaza aufruft.	9
«Stay with Gaza», il messaggio della Thunberg e di altre attiviste nella foto pubblicata sabato online.	9
Otras tres personas aparecen con sendos car/etes con las frases "Palestina libre", "Justicia climática ya!"	7
Greta Thunberg publicerade ett inlägg i fredags på sociala medier-plattformen X, där hon och andra aktivister höll upp handskrivna plakat med budskapen "Stå upp för Gaza" och "Befria Palestina".	5
Ministerul israelian al Educației a anunțat că va elimina orice referințe la activista pentru climă Greta Thunberg, după ce aceasta a publicat în weekend o postare în care ținea o pancartă...	1

'Number of articles: 2113'
 'Articles from disinfo: 285'

Story: 0: "COP28: Global Climate Change Discussions and Actions"
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 Name_Calling-Labeling: 4493
 Obfuscation-Vagueness-Confusion: 165
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0: Förra veckan dömdes Greta Thunberg till böter för ohörsamhet mot ordningsmakten efter en klimat...
 1: "Fără ambasadă evrească pe pământ arabi!"
 2: Environmental group Greenpeace said two of its activists scaled the Intercontinental Hotel in May
 3: Hier sehen Sie den Beitrag von Greta Thunberg.
 4: In einem Beitrag heißt es » Free Palestine from the river to the sea.«
 5: Video footage showed Thunberg, wearing a badge with the slogan "Oil Money Out" standing call...
 6: t muss ihre Stimme erheben und einen sofortigen Waffenstillstand, Gerechtigkeit und Freiheit für...
 7: „Stop Financing Fossil Fuels“, was auf Deutsch in etwa übersetzt in etwa:
 8: Fossil Free London activists banged drums and chanted "oil, oil money, out, out, out" as they bl...
 9: (Kiemelt képpönként Greta Thunberg svéd klímaaktivista reagál, amikor egy rendőrségi furgon felé...
 10: Auf Plakaten stand zum Beispiel „Make Polluters Pay“ (übersetzt etwa:
 11: *) Sie spielte damit offenkundig auf die von Israel besetzten palästinensischen Gebiete an.
 12: *) Sie spielte damit offenkundig auf die von Israel besetzten palästinensischen Gebiete an.
 13: Thunberg was among dozens of protesters who chanted oil money out and attempted to block...
 14: Several hundred protesters gathered by the InterContinental London Park Lane hotel during the...
 15: Thunberg war zuletzt auch wegen ihrer Position im Nahostkonflikt in die Diskussion geraten.
 16: Outside the forum, demonstrators banged drums and chanted "stop the oil, stop the gas" and "W...
 17: oft banners and chanted "oil money out" and "cancel the conference," while some lit yellow and...
 18: „No climate justice on occupied land.“

Article Snippet	count
" („Auf besetztem Land gibt es keine Klimagerechtigkeit.	75
"No climate justice on occupied land.	35
" („Auf besetztem Land gibt es keine Klimagerechtigkeit.	34
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« Pas de justice climatique sur les terres occupées »,.	1

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 'Articles from disinfo: 23'

